

A NEW INFILTRATION MODELLING FOR FABRICATION PROCESS OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper relates to fabrication processing analysis of metal matrix composites by the injection of liquid metal into a fibrous preform. One dimensional heat transfer analysis during squeeze infiltration process of aluminum base composites has been studied, and the finite difference technique has been adopted. An analysis method is presented describing the temperature distribution, infiltration velocity and melt infiltration characteristics in home made preform with random fiber array.

INTRODUCTION

The metal matrix composites [MMCs] have been fabricated by the squeeze infiltration process which have been the most successful method of various techniques. In a liquid infiltration process, an estimation of infiltration phenomenon is a necessity for the fabrication of the composite parts.

In an adiabatic infiltration process, heat will be exchanged between matrix and fiber[1]~[6]. In a nonadiabatic fabrication process, heat transfer will additionally take place between the composites and die walls, as is usually the case in conventional casting process. These heat transfer phenomena are of importance, because they influence both infiltration limitation and the reaction between fiber and molten metal. When molten metal is infiltrated in a fibrous preform with random orientation, phase transformation will be occur in a region such as molten metal, solidified region, preform region and infiltration composites region. Heat transfer analysis with phase change is very difficult to clarify temperature distribution and infiltration limits of each region in the squeeze infiltration process. In this present paper, a mathematical modelling of solidification phenomena in fabrication process of MMCs using a squeeze infiltration technique investigated by the basic relations for of liquid metal into a fibrous preform, and provide temperature distribution in each region, velocity

variation in the infiltration front.

The theoretical background on infiltration process

Fig.1 schematically illustrates the phase change phenomena during infiltration of the molten metal region ⑤ into preform region ① held within a mold with several squeeze casting conditions. In general squeeze casting for MMCs fabrication, the initial preform temperature T_p , the preheated mold temperature T_m , and initial molten metal temperature T_l at the pouring start point are all different from one another. The preform temperature are initially at a temperature lower than that of the molten metal, and heat transfer will occur locally from base alloy to preform. The composites region ④ containing liquid metal occurs at the initiate infiltration . The composites region ③ containing semi-solid base alloy occurs owing to heat transfer between preform and mold wall. In region ②, superheated base metal entering the preform will remelt to solid metal containing preform. The infiltration problem considering heat transfer between the die and materials is very difficult, because phase change with variation of infiltration time occurs.

Solidification analysis

Fig.2 shows coordinate system of the unidirectional solidification model which the flow is terminated by the formation of the solidified layer in the infiltration front $X_2=X_c$. The initial thickness of the preform is given as X_0 . The length

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the solidification phenomena surrounding the preform

Fig.2 The simplified mathematical model

X_c of the composite material increases with infiltration, and the length X_l of the molten metal region decreases with the increasing of the infiltration. When the temperature of molten metal and the preform are T_l , T_p respectively, the surrounding wall is adiabatic, and the temperature of upper and lower die are $T_r=T_d$, respectively. The heat equilibrium equations for the molten metal region ①, the composites region ② containing both liquid state and preform region ⑤ can be written as following, respectively.

$$\nabla \cdot (k_l \nabla T_l) = \rho_l C_l \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial t} + \rho_l C_l V_o \nabla T_l - \rho_l H \frac{\partial F_s(t)}{\partial t} \quad : 0 \leq X_l \leq X_e \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (k_c \nabla T_c) = \rho_c C_c \frac{\partial T_c}{\partial t} + \rho_l C_l V_o \nabla T_c \quad : 0 \leq X_2 \leq X_c \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (k_p \nabla T_p) = \rho_p C_p \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} \quad : X_0 - X_c \leq X_2 \leq X_o \quad (3)$$

Solid fraction $F_s(t)$ used in Eq. (1) is linearly distributed over the temperature due to increase of specific heat in the range of liquidus T_L to solidus T_S . Because the fibrous preform of region ⑤ contains air in the inner, the thermal properties is determined the rule of mixture. During solidification, heat is generated due to evolution of latent heat depends upon the fraction of solid formed. The present study is largely based on simplified an equivalent specific heat for the phase-change process during infiltration process. The heat transfer equation (1)(2) due to specific heat change in a liquid region ①, liquid metal region ② containing fibers and mushy region ③ were modified.

The governing equation with coordinate transformation

In the fabrication process of MMCs with squeeze infiltration method, numerical analysis is very difficult because each region size and boundary change according to time. Therefore, the moving boundary between liquid, composites

Fig.3 Physical and transformation plane for calculation

and preform can be fixed by the coordinate transformation as shown in Fig.3. The next three independent variables are introduced for the present case.

$$\text{Liquid region} \quad : \quad \xi = \frac{X_1}{X_l} \quad : \quad 0 < \xi < 1 \quad (0 < X_1 < X_l) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Composite region} \quad : \quad \eta = \frac{X_2}{X_c} \quad : \quad 0 < \eta < 1 \quad (0 < X_2 < X_c) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Preform region} \quad : \quad \zeta = \frac{X_2 - X_c}{X_0 - X_c} \quad : \quad 0 < \zeta < 1 \quad (X_c < X_2 < X_0) \quad (6)$$

By using Eqs.(4)(5)(6), the transferred heat transfer equation for Eqs. (1)(2) and (3) are written as following, respectively.

$$\rho_l C_{le} \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial t} = (\rho_l C_{le} \xi \frac{\partial X_l}{\partial t} - \rho_l C_l V_0) \frac{1}{X_l} \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial \xi} + k_l \frac{1}{X_l^2} \frac{\partial^2 T_l}{\partial \xi^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\rho_c C_{ce} \frac{\partial T_c}{\partial t} = (\rho_c C_{ce} \eta \frac{\partial X_c}{\partial t} - \rho_c C_l V_0) \frac{1}{X_c} \frac{\partial T_c}{\partial \eta} + k_c \frac{1}{X_c^2} \frac{\partial^2 T_c}{\partial \eta^2} \quad (8)$$

$$\rho_p C_p \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} = \rho_p C_p \frac{(1-\zeta)}{(X_0 - X_c)} \frac{\partial X_c}{\partial t} \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial \zeta} + k_p \frac{1}{(X_0 - X_c)^2} \frac{\partial^2 T_p}{\partial \zeta^2} \quad (9)$$

The boundary conditions at the interface of each region also can be rewritten as following, respectively

$$\xi = 1 \quad : \quad k_l \frac{1}{X_l} \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial \xi} = h(T_l - T_r) \quad (10)$$

$$\xi = 0, \eta = 0 \quad : \quad -k_l \frac{1}{X_l} \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial \xi} = k_c \frac{1}{X_c} \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial \eta} \quad (11)$$

$$\zeta = 0, \eta = 1 \quad : \quad k_c \frac{1}{X_c} \frac{\partial T_c}{\partial \eta} = k_p \frac{1}{(X_0 - X_c)} \frac{\partial T_c}{\partial \zeta} \quad (12)$$

$$\zeta = 1 \quad : \quad k_p \frac{1}{(X_0 - X_c)} \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial \zeta} = h(T_p - T_d) \quad (13)$$

The flow of a metal through a fibrous preform is Darcy's flow in proportion to pressure loss, because the metal flow in the fibrous preform of V_0 is very slow. Then, velocity within preform was given as following.

$$V_0 = (1 - V_f) \times V \quad (14)$$

when molten metal was infiltrated in the preform, the moving velocity of infiltration front $X = X_c$ is given by Eq. (15), where, $Y = K_{al} \mu_{air} / K_{air} \mu_{al}$. Infiltration front position X_c at any time t is given as following Eq. (16) [7].

$$V = \frac{K_{al}}{(1 - V_f) \mu_{al}} \frac{\Delta P}{(1 - Y) X_c + Y X_0} \quad (15)$$

$$(1 - Y) \frac{X_c^2}{2} + Y H X_c = \frac{K_{al} \Delta P t}{(1 - V_f) \mu_{al}} \quad (16)$$

Results and Discussion

An explicit type finite difference method scheme was used to solve Eqs. (7)~(9) with boundary condition Eqs. (10)~(13) at the each region. The thermal mechanical properties of base alloy, and thermal properties of short fiber and air properties within fibrous preform used in the calculations are listed in Table 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Table. 1 Thermal properties of base alloy AC8A[8]

ρ_l (kg/m ³)	C_l (J/kg · K)	T_L (K)	T_S (K)	k_l (W/m · K)	H (KJ/kg)
2.713×10^3	963	838	813	117	389

Table. 2 Thermal properties of δ -Alumina

C_f (KJ/kg · K)	d_f (μ m)	$\alpha_f \times 10^6$ (m ² /sec)	k_f (W/m · K)	ρ_f (g/cm ³)
1	3	2	8	3.3

Table. 3 Thermal Properties of Air[9]

ρ_{air} (kg/m ³)	C_{air} (KJ/kg · K)	$\mu_{air} \times 10^7$ (Ns/m ³)	$k_{air} \times 10^3$ (W/m · K)	$\alpha_{air} \times 10^6$ (m ² /sec)
0.5804	1.051	305.8	46.9	76.9

In this articles, heat transfer coefficient in squeeze infiltration process have been limited. Therefore, heat transfer h between preform and base metal in used 20 KWm⁻². Fig. 4 shows temperature distribution in a composite region

Fig.4 Temperature distribution to infiltration time AC8A

Fig.5 Temperature distribution to after complete infiltration

($0 < X_c < 0.05$) and base alloy region ($-0.05 < X_c < 0$) for various a squeeze infiltration time. Temperature variation in composites region is almost constant except $X_c = 0.05\text{m}$ of lower die position. It is founded that temperature is remarkably decrease due to heat flow between die and materials. This is thought that the heat conductivity of fiber is much smaller than that of matrix, as show in Table.1. Fig. 4 is a not fully infiltrated state for same preform thickness, namely, solidification is generated within the preform before infiltration is completed. The infiltration length depends on initial temperature of molten metal. Fig. 5 shows temperature distribution in a fully infiltrated region (composites region) for preform thickness of $X_c = 50\text{mm}$. At the initial infiltration time $t = 1.4\text{sec}$, temperature distribution in the vicinity of upper die ($X_c = 0$) is higher than that of lower die ($X_c = 0.05$) due to the effects of initial temperature of the infiltrated matrix within preform thickness. After infiltration time $t = 5.8\text{sec}$, the temperature distribution is a symmetric in the range from upper die ($X_c = 0$) to lower die ($X_c = 0.05$) due heat transfer between die and materials (matrix alloy and composites). Perfect solidification in composites region ($0 \leq X_c \leq 0.05$) after infiltration occurs in $t = 6.9\text{sec}$ below solidus $T_s = 838\text{K}$. Fig. 6 shows the temperature distribution in the infiltration front. The temperature of infiltration front is decrease with an increasing of infiltration length at the same temperature of molten metal. It is found that the effect of infiltration front temperature on infiltration distance in depend on initial temperature of molten metal than that of mold.

Fig.6 Temperature variation at infiltration front

Fig.7 The relation of cooling rate and infiltration distance

Fig. 7 shows cooling rate in a infiltration front. Cooling rate is sharply decrease with an increasing of infiltration length during initial infiltration ($0 < X_c < 5$), and cooling rate is a constant as infiltration is progressing.

Fig. 8 shows velocity variation in infiltration front calculated using Eq. (15)(16). Infiltration velocity remarkably decrease with increasing infiltration distance. The decreasing of velocity in initial infiltration state is probably caused by reduction of permeability due to solidification of molten metal on the fibers. Fig.9 shows the relation of infiltration distance with infiltration time. The preform of the thickness 50mm has been infiltrated in the time 1.3 sec in case of AC8A with superheat $\Delta T=160K$. Preform thickness 24mm has been infiltrated in the 0.5sec for superheat 60K. During infiltration process, friction force is happened from local solidification of matrix in the vicinity of mold. Furthermore, the analysis considering the friction force between fiber and molten matrix is also important to estimate infiltration phenomena. In this paper, flow velocity and infiltration pressure were calculated with uncoupling problems. Furthermore, to more correct estimate of infiltration phenomena, two dimensional infiltration analysis considering a coupled modelling of infiltration pressure and solidification will be necessary to get more insight into the nonadiabatic fabrication effect in infiltration process.

Fig.8 The relation of infiltration velocity and infiltration distance

Fig.9 The relation of infiltration distance and infiltration time

CONCLUSIONS

The influence of the die temperature on the infiltration front temperature and infiltration length are not significant. Even though the initial molten metal temperature has a great influence on the infiltration length and velocity, the influence of the temperature distribution within a fibrous preform is minor.

A fully infiltration time under a fabrication conditions of $T_i=973K$, $T_p=573K$ and $T_d=573K$ with base alloy AC8A is calculated to be 1.2 sec for preform thickness 50mm and punch velocity 18 mm/sec.

Nomenclature

C	: specific heat(J/kgK)	μ	: viscosity (N·S/m ²)
H	: latent heat(kJ/kg)	ϵ	: porosity (1-Vf)
k	: thermal conductivity (W/mK)	ρ	: density(kg/m ³)
K	: permeability		
P	: pressure(N/m ²)		
ΔP	: infiltration pressure(N/m ²)		
t	: time(sec)		
T	: temperature(K)	c	: composites
V	: velocity (m/sec)	p	: preform
Vf	: volume fraction (%)	d	: die
X ₁ , X ₂	: coordinate system(m)	air	: air
X _c , X ₁ , X ₀	: composites matrix and preform thickness, respectively(m)	f	: fiber
		al	: base alloy
		l	: molten metal

Subscript

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